

A Review of Peer Pressure and Its Relationship with Personality Outcomes in Higher Education Students

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ABSTRACT

In particular, the research highlights the importance of students' contacts with their peers in shaping their personalities by investigating the link between peer pressure and students' personality outcomes. Peer pressure, defined as the influence exerted by peers to encourage specific behaviors, leads to increasing similarities among peers over time. The findings suggest that socialization with peers significantly impacts personality traits, particularly in the university setting, where positive peer relationships contribute to the development of traits beneficial for academic success, such as cooperation and a prosocial value orientation. This review underscores the dual nature of peer pressure, presenting both challenges and opportunities for student growth.

Keywords; Peer pressure, Personality development, Student, Strengths, Self-regulation

INTRODUCTION

Having easy conversational and social interactions with one's peers is good. All young people rely on them heavily. Since they are together for the most of the day, it seems to reason that they would desire to observe and follow one another's every move. Peer pressure throughout youth helps with both the emotional and physical development of a person by encouraging them to help and support one another. The reality is, however, that it may sometimes hurt them. Consequently, it is essential to have a healthy balance in terms of peer influence. Teens might take up comparable actions only by believing that their peers approve of them, rather than seeing and adopting them, says the Social Learning Theory. Peers have a profound impact on adolescents in several ways, including their appearance, speech, eating habits, sexual behaviour, use of social media, adoption and acceptance of anti-social and violent behaviours, and many more.

The goal of personality development, in its simplest form, is to bring about desirable changes in an individual's character. An individual's inherent abilities and talents may be better understood via this procedure. Nevertheless, these transformations take time. Because doing so requires patience. Furthermore, other elements, such as individual behaviour, thought patterns, reaction patterns, etc., largely determine the outcomes.

When people imitate the actions of their friends, this is known as peer influence. More so than any other age group, adolescents follow it mindlessly. They go so far as to confide in their peers and even try to be believed by them as role models. Being careful is essential throughout adolescence since it is a sensitive period that affects everyone. At this stage, the person is full of life and excitement. In every aspect of existence, this is a time of growth and progress. A person's character and personality are shaped throughout this time, allowing them to become a better version of themselves and impacting their fate. While that is happening, more individuals are likely to get involved in harmful habits like drug abuse. Identifying students' transitions from one position to another and pointing them in the right direction might be a crucial responsibility of college instructors.

Every person's perception, thought process, and behavioural habits are shaped by their distinct personality. Family and environment, in addition to an individual's inherent traits, have a role in shaping their personality. An individual's personality encompasses all of their behaviours and is constantly shaped by their internal and external environments. During the time spent at college or university, a person's social, physical, and psychological well-being, as well as their behaviour and character characteristics, undergo significant growth.

This is in addition to being the last stage of puberty. Whether in a small or big group, young people acquire power, belonging, and self-assurance, according to earlier studies. People form these groups when they and their friends decide to do something together that none of them would have done on their own. Joining one of these organisations is a certain way to gain social status, independence, and the ability to form both positive and negative routines. So, for the majority of people, their peer groups are the primary arbiters of whether their views and actions are acceptable or not.

The term "peer pressure" describes the kind of social pressure that members of a peer group exert on one another to conform to their expectations. One possible interpretation is that it's when one peer puts pressure on another to act in a way that their peers find acceptable. Children and students need good advice from adults, such as teachers and parents, to navigate the inevitable pressures of peer pressure. Adolescents are vulnerable to the powerful influences of their peers, which may have both beneficial and harmful outcomes. Poor academic performance, low self-esteem, feelings of isolation, despair, and lack of confidence are all caused by it. Take a look at how peer pressure works.

LITERATURE REVIEW

(Mathew & Simon, 2024) The results demonstrated that there were significant relationships and differences between academic stress and self-regulation, peer pressure and self-regulation, and academic stress and academic stress among college students. In addition, peer pressure had a substantial influence on academic stress but no apparent effect on self-regulation. These findings emphasise the need of addressing academic stress and peer pressure in order to promote good self-regulation and overall well-being among college students, as well as the complex interactions that affect them.

(Bică, 2023) Even if mistreating a stranger who is trying to do the best by everyone is the group's unjust behaviour, those with high SA tend to join in. Interestingly, high SA individuals prioritise group conformity above prosocial reciprocity, in contrast to the broader population that follows the norms of reciprocity. Our results demonstrate, when aggregated, that SA-high individuals are more obedient to collective demands.

(Kumar Yadav & Kumari, 2023) High school seniors have dealt with a variety of issues pertaining to the influence of classmates on their academic performance, including issues of social belonging, parental cultural orientation, academic inclination, and academic rigour. Based on the findings, it seems that there are a number of variables related to peer pressure that could influence students' academic achievement. This data demonstrates that students are not adversely affected by peer pressure. Peer pressure in the classroom has a wide-ranging impact on pupils' ability to learn and retain information.

(No et al., 2022) Peers influence one another; students who are already competitive tend to become even more so; students whose friends are more tolerant and accepting tend to broaden their perspectives; and students whose friends are already diligent tend to be even more so. The agreeableness, neuroticism, and extraversion of one's peers do not seem to have any discernible impact. Personality qualities that are predictive of performance have the greatest impact on one's performance, as predicted by the model. College life is a social environment where students pick up characteristics that will serve them well. Our research shows that interacting with one's peers may have an effect on one's character development.

(Wang & Hu, 2021) College students' cooperative inclinations were examined in this research, along with the mediating and modifying roles of interpersonal trust and social value orientation, in connection to their peer interactions. In instance, compared to pro-self college students, pro-social students were more receptive to peer interactions. College students who are socially orientated and have strong friendships with their classmates are more likely to be cooperative, according to the results of this research.

(Bart et al., 2017) By demonstrating how peer personality impacts educational attainment, this study offers proof of a new aspect of peer effects. Our research, which takes use of the fact that university sections are randomly assigned, shows that students fare better when they are in the company of more persistent and less risk-taking classmates. In instance, students who struggle to maintain focus could learn from their more persistent classmates without having to put in any more time or energy themselves. On the other hand, the perseverance of other students has little effect on kids who are very persistent. Different from other observable peer qualities, the personality peer effects found indicate that peers' personality traits directly impact human capital accumulation.

(Deepika & Prema, 2017) Examining how deviant students' academic performance is impacted by peer pressure was the primary goal of this research. Concerning the relationship between peer pressure and academic performance, the results showed no statistically significant difference between males and females. The 16–18 age bracket was more susceptible to peer pressure to engage in antisocial behaviour than other younger age brackets. Academic performance is negatively correlated with peer pressure, and this research confirms that peer pressure is a major factor in this decline.

CONCLUSION

Peer pressure plays a significant role in shaping the personality outcomes of students, influencing various aspects of their academic and social lives. Academic stress, for instance, is notably affected by peer pressure, although its impact on self-regulation is less apparent. Graduating high school students experience peer pressure in diverse ways, shaped by factors such as social belonging, curiosity, and cultural-parenting orientations, all of which are linked to their academic pursuits. When students are in an environment where they see a lot of competition, they are likely to adopt some of that attitude themselves. On the other hand, if students are in an environment where they see a lot of open-mindedness or conscientiousness, they are likely to adopt some of those virtues as well. Additionally, in the university context, students often develop personality traits that are advantageous for academic success, with positive peer relationships fostering a cooperative spirit and a prosocial value orientation. These dynamics underscore the importance of peer interactions in the development of students' personalities, highlighting both the challenges and the growth opportunities that peer pressure presents.

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